

Establishing Acceptability Thresholds for Matooke Colour And Texture

Kampala, Uganda, 17/03/2025

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This report has been written in the framework of the RTB Breeding project, Quality-component (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods project.

To be cited as:

Kephas NOWAKUNDA, Moreen ASASIRA, Sarah KISAKYE, Mary Gorreth NAMUDDU, Elizabeth KHAKASA, Living TUKASHABA, Amos ASIIMWE (2025). *Establishing Acceptability Thresholds for Matooke Colour And Texture.* Kampala, Uganda: RTB Breeding project, Scientific Report, 25 p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15117872>

Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the RTB Breeding project, through a sub-grant from the International Potato Center (CIP) to the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), Montpellier, France, incorporated in the grant agreement INV-041105 between CIP and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF).

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ACRONYMS

JAR	Just About Right
NARL	National Agricultural Research Laboratories
RTB	Root, Tubers and Bananas
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TPA	Textural Profile Analysis
QDA	Quantitative Descriptive Analysis
WP	Work package

ABSTRACT

This report presents the results of a consumer testing study aiming to determine thresholds for acceptability of the quality traits of steamed Matooke. The aim of acceptability thresholds is to obtain measurable values for the intensity of key sensory characteristics corresponding to consumer acceptability: color and Texture of steamed Matooke in Uganda. The activity was conducted at the peri-urban location of Kawanda, Wakiso District in the central region. Ten matooke varieties with contrasting quality characteristics were processed into steamed matooke and presented to consumers for evaluation. Four local varieties Kibuzi, Mbwazirume, Nakitembe, and Nfuuka, and six hybrids NARITA 17, M30, M9, NARITA 9, NARITA 13, and NARITA 22 were used in the exercise. The threshold values were determined through consumer testing using a 9-point hedonic scale and just-about-right (JAR) tests, Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) by a trained panel, and Instrumental analysis with a Chroma Meter and a TMS-Pilot texture analyzer for color and texture respectively following threshold determination methodological procedure. The analysis was done using means and ANOVAs in XLSTAT.

The results showed that the consumers perceived the matooke products from the ten varieties differently which were discriminant for texture and color. Nakitembe, Kibuzi, Nfuuka, and Mbwazirume gave a mean overall liking score of 7.89, 7.83, 7.8 and 7.5 ('like very much') respectively. Matooke hybrids NARITA 17, had mean overall liking of 7 ("like moderately"), M30 had mean liking of 6. M9, NARITA 22, with a mean liking of 5, (nether neither liked nor disliked) and NARITA 13 and NARITA 9 had mean values of 3 "dislike moderately" respectively. Results further indicate that the acceptable instrumental color ranged between 27.5 and ≥ 29.5 from arbitrary chosen consumer JAR levels of 60% and 70% respectively. More still, for JAR softness and instrumental cohesiveness, for more than 60% of the consumers to be satisfied, instrumental cohesiveness should be more than 0.55 and the optimal threshold where 70% of the consumers are satisfied as greater than 0.87. Instrumental hardness acceptability threshold was reportedly between 2 and 2.6 ($\text{hardness} \leq 2.6$).

Key Words: Matooke, Quality traits, Threshold, QDA, instrumental, Color, Texture

1.0. INTRODUCTION

The work presented in this report covers activities conducted under RTB breeding for quality, a project component that proceeded RTBFoods work packages 1 (WP1) and 2 (WP2).

Breeding programs have enhanced the crop by developing matooke banana varieties with superior agronomic traits like resistance to pests, diseases and several environmental stress factors (Tumuhimbise *et al.*, 2018). Culinary characteristics of the matooke hybrids are critical to their acceptability. Including culinary attributes among the main criteria for selection earlier in the process could support the breeding of improved varieties with consumer-preferred traits. For instance, consumers of steamed Matooke in Uganda have expressed a preference for varieties that have bright yellow color, moldable, not hardening quickly, smooth, with uniform texture in the mouth, good aroma and taste (Akankwasa *et al.*, 2022).

To increase chances of getting an acceptable hybrid, matooke banana breeders generate thousands of genotypes. The genotypes are screened using sensory methods (Nowakunda *et al.*, 2019) to identify acceptable ones. While use of sensory panels and consumer acceptability tests are the most accurate measures for human sensory perception and liking, however, time and other resources remain a challenge (Meilgaard *et al.*, 2007). High throughput instrumental methods which can be used to assess a large number of samples in a short time could facilitate the screening process if they are correlated with the human assessment of sensory attributes that are linked with end-user preferences. Texture (specifically, the perceived softness and mouthfeel) and color (yellowness of matooke and homogeneity) are key sensory attributes that influence consumer acceptance of steamed matooke (Khakasa *et al.*, 2023).

For Matooke in Uganda, RTB Foods WP1 and WP2 generated several SOPs and tools to support consumer-led breeding including: the product profile for steamed Matooke, protocols for sensory analysis (Consumer tests, quantitative descriptive sensory analysis, and texture analysis of cooking bananas). Under RTB Breeding for quality, acceptability thresholds aim to obtain measurable values for the intensity of key sensory characteristics corresponding to consumer acceptability for effective consumer-guided banana breeding and improvement.

In this study, existing data from descriptive sensory analysis conducted during the RTBFoods guided selection of genotypes with varying characteristics, and the proposed thresholds were applied to ensure that they met consumer preferences. Next, the cooking banana varieties were sourced from farmers and breeding fields. The varieties were prepared and served to consumers for evaluation in concurrence with QDA and instrumental analyses (Marimo *et al.* 2019, Nowakunda *et al.* 2019). The data collected were used to determine the threshold levels for the quality traits of color and texture based on the determination of methodological guidelines.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

Consumer testing was conducted in the purposively selected peri-urban location in Wakiso in central region. Consumer testing was conducted at Nkokonjeru zone in Kawanda ward, Nabweru division. The area was selected for the consumer evaluations due to its proximity to the research institute where laboratory analyses would be possible to conduct alongside consumer testing evaluations at the same time. Also, the area population is considered representative of all consumer categories of Matooke like farmers, traders, and pure consuming groups.

2.2 Sampling

Being an urban area, one ward contained enough households for the consumer testing exercise. The Local Council (LC) chairperson helped recruit consumers from different villages surrounding the location. The selection criteria included, one being above eighteen years of age, a matooke consumer and availability to participate in the exercise. The Local council committee members randomly selected the respondents from the registers at the local council office registry. Respondents were contacted by phone and those unavailable, were contacted physically by the chairperson or any committee member available. In case of unavailability on the testing day, a replacement was made either by the eldest member in the household or the next household in the list to maintain the sample size for both days of evaluation.

2.3 Samples and Variety Selection

Ten contrasting banana genotypes (local and hybrids) with varying sensory characteristics were selected for the study. The genotypes selected were representative of the most preferred, moderate and least preferred genotypes based on varietal profiling RTBfoods project findings (Akankwasa *et al.*,2022). The hybrids used were either released (M9, M30, or promising based on the periodic consumer acceptability studies. The fully matured selected genotypes were sourced from farmers and breeding fields for both local and hybrids. Upon harvest, each genotype was labeled with a unique code and transported by car to the evaluation site for preparation .

Table 1: Varieties used during threshold determination

Genotype	Local/hybrid	selection rationale	Characteristics(cooked)
Nakitembe	Local	Most preferred	Soft, yellow color, good taste
M30	Hybrid	Moderate	fairly soft, fairly yellow color
Mbwazirume	Local	Most preferred	soft, moldable, yellow color
NARITA 22	Hybrid	Fair	fairly yellow, fairly firm
M9	Hybrid	Moderate	fairly soft, fairly yellow color
NARITA 9	Hybrid	Fair	fairly soft, fairly yellow color
Nfuuka	Local	Most preferred	moldable, soft, yellow
NARITA 13	Hybrid	Fair	very soft, sticky
NARITA 17	Hybrid	Moderate	fairly yellow, moldable

2.4 Sensory Analysis

2.4.1 Preparation of samples:

The green mature cooking bananas were peeled, wrapped in banana leaves, and steamed under the same cooking conditions (Marimo *et al.*, 2021) in two separate big saucepans as separate bundles marked with distinct colour strings to ease identification.

2.4.1 Consumer testing

The consumers (100) were randomly recruited from the peri-urban outskirts of Kawanda parish in Nabweru division in the Central region. Ethical approval for human participation in this study had earlier been obtained from the Makerere University School of Social Sciences Research Ethics Committee (MAKSSREC).

The consumer testing questionnaire used in this study was similar to the one used in prior evaluations with a few modifications. Enumerators were trained to administer the questionnaire to previously invited respondents using appropriate local languages mostly Luganda and English. At the beginning of the interview, enumerators sought informed consent from the participants. Samples were served one at a time for evaluation.

Consumers first evaluated the general overall liking of the samples on a 9-point hedonic scale using a list of characteristics previously generated with matooke users (Akankwasa *et al.*, 2022). Genotypes were then tasted one at a time in terms of color, softness by touch and mouth feel using a Just- About-Right (JAR) scale.

The respondents rated the overall liking of each sample on a nine-point hedonic scale ranging from 1 (“dislike extremely”) to 9 (“like extremely”). They also rated samples for color, mouthfeel, and softness on a three -point Just-About-Right (JAR) scale ranging from 1 to 3. Upon completing the interview, respondents were given a small token of appreciation. All data was entered in Excel, cleaned and analyzed in XLSTAT.

Figure 1: Matooke bunches used, preparation and serving

2.4.2. Descriptive sensory analysis using quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA)

Quantitative descriptive sensory evaluation was performed by 12-member trained panel at the Food Biosciences Laboratories, NARL-Kawanda to establish the sensory quality of the matooke. Matooke samples for quantitative descriptive sensory analysis were prepared following established standard operating procedures (SOP). The sensory parameters assessed were: softness by touch, mouthfeel, taste, moldability, smell, texture, attractiveness, hardness by touch and appearance. Samples were evaluated and scored against the developed descriptors. The appearance of matooke was described by color and homogeneity of the color, while the texture was described by firmness, moistness and smoothness all by mouth, while hardness by touch and moldability were by touch. One sample was served at a time on disposable plates and presented with a glass of water for rinsing their mouths.

2.5 Instrumental texture analysis of Matooke samples

Portions of the same samples were transported to the laboratory for analyzing the quantitative indicators for instrumental analyses. The texture of each sample portion was analyzed using a TMS-Pilot texture analyzer following a texture profile analysis (TPA) procedure (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00602>).

2.6 Determination of colour

Cooked matooke colour was determined according to Khakasa et al., 2024 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foohum.2024.100268>). A Konica Minolta chroma metre, CR-400 was used to measure colour intensity of cooked matooke in terms of lightness (L*), greenness (a*), and yellowness (b*).

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Correlations between instrumental and sensory parameters were performed using XLSTAT. The thresholds for color and texture were determined based on the correlations between various sensory attributes, using the selected arbitrary points of satisfied consumers from the scatter plots using JAR and/or instrumental values as a function of QDA measurements following the threshold determination procedure (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/0078>).

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Consumer acceptability of matooke varieties

3.1.1 Overall liking

Most preferred matooke genotypes were Nakitembe, Kibuzi and Nfuuka with mean overall liking scores of 7.89, 7.83 and 7.80 (close to 8 or like very much) respectively. There were no significant differences in the average scores for Nakitembe and Kibuzi, Mbwazirume and NARITA 17 with mean scores of 7.45 and 7.07 (much liked), M30, M9 and NARITA 22 (Moderately liked) and NARITA 13, NARITA 9 with a mean score of 2.1 and 2.69 (close to dislike moderately) (**Figure 2**)

Figure 2: Consumers overall liking for matooke genotypes

3.1.2 JAR scores

The landraces Kibuzi, Nakitembe, Mbwazirume, and Nfuuka were the most highly scored as JAR for color by the consumers, and the closest hybrid scored JAR was NARITA 17. The landraces Kibuzi, Nakitembe, Mbwazirume, and Nfuuka were highly scored as JAR for softness by the consumers, and the closest hybrid scored JAR was NARITA 17 and M30. The landraces KIBUZI, NAKITEMBE, MBWAZIRUME, and NFUUKA were highly scored as JAR Mouthfeel by the consumers, and the closest hybrids scored JAR were NARITA 17 and M30 (**Figure 3, 4 and 5**).

Figure 3: Consumer scores for JAR Color intensity

Figure 4: Consumer scores for JAR softness

Figure 5: Consumer scores for JAR mouthfeel

3.2 Quantitative descriptive analysis of matooke varieties

Results of the descriptive analysis are presented in Table 2. Most genotypes were scored above average for yellow color intensity on the scale. This suggests that according to the QDA, all genotypes have a yellow color intensity greater than 5, with the exception of NARITA 13 and NARITA 9 which had mean scores of 1.8 and 1.3 respectively. Likewise, for texture, genotypes were reportedly smooth in the mouth except for NARITA 13 and NARITA 22.

Table 2: Mean scores of various sensory attributes of Matooke genotypes evaluated

Geno type	QDA		Firmn ess M	Moist ure M	Smoot hness	Hardn ess T	Molda bility	Sticki ness	Cohesiv eness	Hard ness	Adhesiv eness	Spring iness	Gumm iness	Chewi ness
	Yellowne ss	Homogene ity												
Kibuz														
i	8.60	8.40	1.00	8.44	9.05	1.00	8.80	2.46	0.83	0.98	-0.01	0.88	0.79	0.69
M30	6.00	7.45	2.45	6.80	7.91	2.60	8.27	2.00	0.68	4.51	-0.13	0.50	2.46	1.06
M9	6.10	7.10	2.60	6.89	7.70	2.89	8.20	2.83	0.88	2.31	-0.03	0.85	2.22	1.93
Mbw	7.80	8.00	1.44	7.56	8.40	1.33	8.70	1.63	0.67	1.13	-0.07	0.66	0.76	0.50
NKT	7.55	8.27	1.64	7.50	8.27	2.27	8.50	1.67	0.58	2.22	-0.18	0.55	1.25	0.65
N13	1.80	0.70	2.56	6.56	6.60	3.00	7.80	4.00	0.82	1.22	-0.01	0.84	1.49	1.34
N17	7.10	7.70	1.80	7.89	8.30	1.80	8.70	3.17	0.89	1.54	-0.02	0.88	1.43	1.32
N22	3.27	3.60	4.00	4.82	6.73	4.36	7.18	1.40	0.51	6.58	-0.29	0.39	3.29	1.31
N9	1.30	0.89	2.09	7.00	7.30	2.36	7.40	2.67	0.59	5.34	-0.17	0.49	3.16	1.58
NFK	8.09	8.55	2.50	6.95	8.46	2.15	8.77	1.90	0.64	9.57	-0.39	0.60	6.04	3.40

Mbw=Mbwazirume, NKT=Nakitembe, NFK=Nfuuka, N=NARITA

3.3 Relationships between sensory and Instrumental parameters

3.3.1 Correlations between sensory and Instrumental parameters

There were significant correlations between stickiness and cohesiveness, springiness and resilience ($P < 0.05$). The instrumental Hardness was significantly correlated with sensory firmness in the mouth ($P < 0.01$). Instrumental adhesiveness was significantly correlated with stickiness by touch ($P < 0.01$). Instrumental springiness was also significantly correlated with sensory moisture in mouth ($P < 0.01$). Sensory hardness was not significantly correlated with any instrumental textural properties. Sensory stickiness was significantly correlated with cohesiveness ($r=0.743$) and springiness (0.707). Sensory Hardness was however negatively weakly correlated with textural properties like cohesiveness (-0.38) Adhesiveness (-0.378) and instrumental hardness (0.413).

Table 3: Pearson Correlations between sensory and Instrumental texture

	Hardness (N)	Adhesiveness (N.mm)	Cohesiveness (-)	Springiness (-)	Gumminess (N)	Chewiness (N)	Resilience (-)
	Coefficient						
Yellow	-0.1401	0.0179	0.2239	0.2917	-0.1251	-0.0418	0.1773
Homogeneity of color	-0.0757	-0.0275	0.1787	0.1946	-0.0749	-0.0210	0.1381
Firmness (mouth)	0.5789	-0.4985	-0.3747	-0.4827	0.5416	0.4014	-0.2553
Moisture (mouth)	-0.5341	0.5109	0.5265	0.6016	-0.4556	-0.2496	0.4347
Smoothness (mouth)	-0.1688	0.0943	0.2346	0.3074	-0.1560	-0.0840	0.1893
Hardness (touch)	0.4128	-0.3789	-0.3806	-0.4802	0.3607	0.2188	-0.2974
Moldability (touch)	-0.2791	0.2004	0.4260	0.4983	-0.1994	-0.0152	0.3425
Stickiness (touch)	-0.4296	0.6265	0.7427	0.7076	-0.2434	0.0878	0.7181
Sweetness	0.0362	-0.1341	-0.0658	0.0863	-0.0271	-0.1042	-0.0869
Astringency	-0.0869	0.2208	0.0977	0.0987	-0.0079	0.0682	0.0738
Sourness	-0.3055	0.3469	0.4027	0.4372	-0.1561	0.0783	0.3057
Matooke aroma	-0.0549	-0.0707	0.0918	0.1228	-0.0848	-0.0728	0.0768
	P value						
Yellow	0.6994	0.9608	0.5340	0.4135	0.7306	0.9087	0.6241
Homogeneity of color	0.8353	0.9399	0.6213	0.5901	0.8371	0.9541	0.7036
Firmness (mouth)	0.0795*	0.1425	0.2861	0.1576	0.1059	0.2502	0.4765
Moisture (mouth)	0.1118	0.1313	0.1180	0.0658*	0.1858	0.4867	0.2093
Smoothness (mouth)	0.6411	0.7955	0.5142	0.3875	0.6669	0.8176	0.6004
Hardness (touch)	0.2358	0.2803	0.2779	0.1601	0.3058	0.5435	0.4040
Moldability (touch)	0.4348	0.5788	0.2196	0.1427	0.5808	0.9668	0.3327
Stickiness (touch)	0.2154	0.0526*	0.0139**	0.0221**	0.4980	0.8094	0.0193**
Sweetness	0.9209	0.7120	0.8566	0.8126	0.9408	0.7745	0.8113
Astringency	0.8113	0.5399	0.7883	0.7862	0.9827	0.8515	0.8394
Sourness	0.3907	0.3260	0.2486	0.2065	0.6668	0.8297	0.3904
Matooke aroma	0.8802	0.8461	0.8008	0.7354	0.8158	0.8415	0.8330

3.3.2 Principal component analysis of sensory and Instrumental textural parameters

Figure 6: Principal component analysis of sensory and Instrumental parameters

The first two principal components comprised 71.66% of the total variance; of which F1 and F2 contributed 45.13% and 26.52% respectively. The PCA results show that moisture in mass, hardness by touch, and firmness in the mouth contributed the most in explaining the variation at F1 followed by mouldability by touch, and not enough softness. On F2, stickiness by touch contributed the most in explaining the variation followed by adhesiveness and resilience. Among all instrumental parameters, hardness was more strongly associated with sensory firmness with the loading lines closest together. Moreover, adhesiveness was mostly associated with stickiness by touch, while cohesiveness was associated with stickiness by touch and moisture in mass. There was a clear contrast among the varieties tested with regards to sensory and instrumental parameters, for example; Kibuzi and NARITA 17 were associated with moisture in mass showing that the varieties have high moisture content when cooked. Mbwazirume and Nakitembe were associated with mouldability, smoothness by mouth, JAR softness, and JAR mouthfeel demonstrating a higher consumer likeability (Akankwasa et al., 2020). Nfuuka and M30 were associated with instrumental hardness, while NARITA 22 was associated with sensory firmness. M9 was associated with too much softness, stickiness, and instrumental adhesiveness.

3.4 Discriminant Analysis for texture of the matooke genotypes

All the TPA textural parameters were discriminant among the matooke genotypes. The most significant textural parameters are springiness and gumminess of cooked matooke. The chewiness is the least discriminant textural property. The landrace Mbwarzirume has low hardness, gumminess and chewiness, and has intermediate adhesiveness, cohesiveness, springiness and resilience that is characteristic of texture of a pasty, slightly soft, inhomogeneous swallow food that matooke is known for (Figure 5).

Figure 7: Discriminant analysis for texture of the matooke genotypes

3.5 Clustering of the Matooke genotypes evaluated

The clustering of cooked matooke genotypes based on TPA texture showed that NFUUKA was clustered separate from other genotypes having the highest level of hardness, gumminess, chewiness and adhesiveness. KIBUZI, NARITA 13, M9 and NARITA 17 were clustered together and had the lowest level of hardness and adhesiveness, but higher levels of cohesiveness and springiness. Genotypes M30, NARITA 9, NARITA 22, MBWAZIRUME and NAKITEMBE were clustered together with intermediate texture.

Figure 8: Clusters of matooke genotypes evaluated

3.6 Thresholds for color and texture

3.6.1 Color thresholds

From the correlations between sensory and instrumental properties, color and texture thresholds were determined in terms of the arbitrarily chosen JAR points/levels at 60 and 70% as acceptable and optimal levels respectively. For instance, for more than 60% of consumers to be satisfied of the color, the Instrumental color was established to be 27.5, and for more than 70% of consumers to be satisfied, the instrumental color measurement must be higher than 29.25. For JAR and QDA yellowness, for more than 60% of Consumers to be satisfied, the QDA score for the color yellow must be higher than 6.6, and for more than 70% of consumers to be satisfied, it must be higher than 7.5. Never the less, for JAR and QDA homogeneity, for more than 60% of consumers to be satisfied, the QDA homogeneity score must be higher than 7.9, and for more than 70% of consumers to be satisfied, it must be higher than 8.25 (Table 4 and figure 9).

Table 4: Sensory and Instrumental thresholds for some color and textural attributes

Colour				
		QDA yellowness	Instrumental color (b)	QDA homogeneity
Mean liking (all attributes)	6.077			
Mean liking by consumers/mean scores		5.761	25.88	6.061
Threshold acceptability at JAR 60%		6.6	27.7	
Threshold acceptability at JAR 70%		8.3	29.3	
Threshold range		6.6 ≥ 8.3	≥ 29.3	
Texture				
Mean firmness (M)	2.21			
Mean hardness (T)	2.37			
Mean Cohesiveness	0.711			
Texture		firmness (QDA)	Hardness (T)	Hardness (INST)
Threshold in terms of JAR softness (60%)		2.3	2.5	2.00
Threshold in terms of JAR softness (70%)		2.8	2.00	≤ 2
Threshold in terms of JAR mouthfeel (60%)		3.2	2.5	0.58
Threshold In terms of JAR mouthfeel (70%)		1.9	1.8	0.85

INST=Instrumental,

Figure 9: Color thresholds

3.6.2 Texture thresholds

Figure 10: Texture thresholds

For JAR softness and QDA hardness textural thresholds, for more than 60% of the consumers to be satisfied, the QDA hardness was rated at be 2.6, and for more than 70% of consumers to be satisfied, QDA hardness was established to be not more than 2.1. Whereas for JAR softness and QDA firmness, for more than 60% of consumers to be satisfied, QDA firmness was 2.5, and for more than 70% to be satisfied, QDA firmness was found to be more than 2.9. The QDA stickiness should be 3.2 for 60% of consumers to be satisfied and not more than 1.6 to satisfy 70% of consumers. Never the less, the results indicate that for JAR softness and instrumental cohesiveness, for more than 60% of the consumers to be satisfied, instrumental cohesiveness was at more than 0.55 and the optimal threshold where 70% of the consumers are satisfied is more than 0.87. In addition, for JAR mouthfeel and instrumental cohesiveness, for 60% of consumers to be satisfied, instrumental cohesiveness should be more than 0.58, and 0.88 for the 70% of consumers to be satisfied (figure 10 and table 4).

3.7 Social demographics of consumers

The steamed matooke genotypes were presented and evaluated 314 consumers, 43% were males and 56 % females with an average age of 32 years old. The consumers had averagely attained 10 years of schooling an equivalent of a secondary school level. Most respondents were married, self-employed and consumed Matooke every or and several days a week (Table 5)

Table 5: Consumer demographics

Variable	N	Percentages
Sex of respondent		
Male	138	43.95
Female	176	56.05
Marital status		
Divorced	14	4.46
Married	170	54.14
Single	119	37.9
Widowed	11	3.5
Age of respondent		
18-24	84	26.75
25-34	108	34.39
35-44	71	22.61
45-54	41	13.06
55-64	6	1.91
>65	4	1.27
Education level (years)		
None	9	3.04
Primary Level	72	24.32

Ordinary Certificate	Level	96	32.43
Advanced Certificate	Level	59	19.93
Higher learning	Institution	60	20.27
Occupation of respondent			
Farmer		25	8.04
Full time employed	Salary	94	30.23
Part time employed	wage	41	13.18
Self employed		114	36.66
Not employed		17	5.46
Student		20	6.43
Frequency of consumption			
Every day		122	38.85
Several times a week		149	47.45
once a week		20	6.37
Several times a month		11	3.5

4.0 CONCLUSION

The study results indicate that consumers perceived the matooke products from the ten Matooke varieties differently. Varieties were discriminant for texture of matooke made from the local genotypes. Kibuzi, Nakitembe, Kibuzi, Nfuuka, and Mbwazirume gave a mean overall liking score in the liking region implying they had the consumer preferred characteristic. More still, results indicate that the acceptable instrumental color level is between 27.5 and the optimal color levels at 29.5 from arbitrary chosen consumer JAR levels of 60% and 70% respectively. For JAR softness and QDA hardness textural thresholds, the acceptable and optimal thresholds were between 2.6 and 2.1. The acceptable threshold levels for JAR softness and instrumental cohesiveness were between 0.55 and 0.87. From the reported correlations between sensory and instrumental properties, it is recommended that more work be done /more sessions to improve on the correlations and or check on the applicability of some sensory attributes being accurately evaluated by instrumental measurements and attaining more feasible improved threshold levels.

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